

Manual for the Implementation of Exercise Interventions

PREVQUEDAS BRASIL RCT

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1. Scope

The exercise programme will consist of two phases: on-site exercises and home exercises, both performed within each patient's pain-free range of motion. On-site exercises will be conducted once a week, supervised by instructors, with a ratio of five older adults per instructor. The aim is that, in 1 hour and 30-minute sessions, 45 minutes are dedicated to standing exercises. Home exercises, once learned by the patients, should be performed for 45 minutes twice a week while the on-site intervention is ongoing, increasing to three times a week once the on-site period has ended.

For balance training, standing posture will be prioritised, as it is well known that this position presents a greater challenge for postural control and offers more benefits for reducing falls, without compromising safety. Emphasis will be placed on progressively challenging static and dynamic balance exercises, aimed at functional training regarding sensory and motor strategies and anticipatory adjustments.

2. GENERAL GUIDELINES

The exercise programme should be led by trained professionals who are familiar with the exercises it includes. During on-site exercise sessions, at least two professionals familiar with the exercise protocol (APPENDIX A) must be present. Only one professional will lead the group, while the others will assist the older adults under supervision.

It is essential that older adults be advised not to exercise on an empty stomach and to wear comfortable clothing and footwear suitable for physical activity.

If a participant has an uncontrolled medical condition during physical activity, the centre's staff responsible for the intervention may reassess the older adult and provide the necessary care.

3. PROCEDURES

3.1 in loco EXERCISES

The description of the on-site exercises is organised according to the physical domains addressed. Before beginning the activities, the responsible professional will record the older adults' weekly

attendance on an attendance sheet. There will be separate lists for the exercise program sessions and the educational sessions.

Trunk muscle stretches will be performed with the patient seated in a chair with a backrest, feet flat and parallel, spine straight, and hands resting on the thighs. Each position will be performed twice, held for 10 seconds with normal breathing, and then returned to the starting position. There will be a ten-second interval between each movement. The first movement will be lateral flexion of the trunk and cervical spine, where the individual will perform lateral flexion of the trunk while keeping the feet on the floor, and the buttocks in contact with the chair seat, with the upper limbs abducted at 90° (parallel to the floor) and elbows extended. The second movement will be the rotation of the trunk and cervical spine. The patient should rotate the trunk, following the movement with their gaze. The hand on the same side as the movement is held suspended at the side of the body, and the other hand rests on the lateral aspect of the thigh on the same side as the movement. This should also be performed once on each side.

IN LOCO EXERCISES

- 13º Stability I (*weight transfer*)
- 14º Stability II (*semi-tandem*)
- 15º Dynamic Balance (*circuit*)

BALANCE

3.1.2 Warm-up

Only in the first session will the seniors perform exercises to stimulate proprioception. To enhance sensitivity in the soles of the feet, a five-minute self-massage will be carried out by sliding the foot over a small, firm ball (e.g., a tennis ball) in all directions, encouraging the patient to notice the mobility of their ankle and foot with each movement, as well as the shifting of body weight. This should be done with one foot at a time. In subsequent sessions, after the stretching, the programme will continue with warm-up exercises involving free movement of the feet while the individual sits in a chair with a backrest. Next, free walking will be performed throughout the exercise area.

Warm-up Exercises

<i>Exercise elements</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Aim</i>	<i>Dosage minimum</i>	<i>Repetitions and intensity</i>	<i>Materials</i>	<i>Safety measures</i>
<i>Proprioception</i>	<i>Postural awareness Ischial support Self-massage with a tennis ball, one foot at a time. Move the ball in all directions and finish by shifting your weight while standing</i>	<i>Stimulate the sensory system to promote greater body awareness</i>	<i>Duration: 5 minutes: - body awareness: 1 minute; - massage: 1 minute per foot; - weight-bearing exercise in a standing position: 1 minute after each massage.</i>	<i>Without progression</i>	<i>Chair Tennis ball</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
<i>Stretching</i>	<i>1. Lateral bending of the trunk and cervical spine while sitting; 2. Rotation of the trunk and cervical spine while sitting, following the movement with the eyes</i>	<i>Improve trunk and head mobility</i>	<i>Duration: 5 minutes: 2 sets of 10 seconds each, with a 10-second break</i>	<i>Without progression</i>	<i>Chair</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
<i>Warm-up</i>	<i>While sitting, move your feet and ankles: plantar flexion, dorsiflexion, inversion, eversion, and circumduction</i>	<i>Improve mobility of the ankle</i>	<i>2 minutes</i>	<i>Without progression</i>	<i>Chair</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
<i>Warm-up</i>	<i>Walk freely around the exercise area. During the walk, you will be asked to increase and decrease your walking speed and stride length</i>	<i>Improve body consciousness while moving around</i>	<i>2 minutes</i>	<i>Without progression</i>	<i>Free space</i>	<i>Supervision</i>

3.1.3 Strength Training

Muscle-strengthening exercises will be integrated into functional activities to enhance and control the movement of the following muscle groups: plantar flexors and ankle dorsiflexors, knee extensors, hip abductors, and hip extensors. All of these are vital for preventing collapse or misalignment of the lower limbs. The progression of the exercises will be tailored to each individual. Strength training exercises will initially be performed without weights. Starting in the third session, 0.5 kg weights will be added gradually. It is expected that by the 12th week, the older adults will be able to perform the exercises with a maximum weight of 2.0 kg.

The aim is for participants to perform the exercises with proper form, avoiding compensatory movements or pain. If a participant reports or shows any discomfort, the professional supervising the intervention should objectively reassess them and revert to the previous stage of progression. To track participants' progress throughout the sessions, a professional must record their performance during the exercises on the progression worksheet during the 1st and 12th sessions. In total, seven muscle-strengthening exercises will be carried out.

Strength Training Exercises

Exercise elements	Description	Aim	Dosage minimum	Repetitions and intensity	Materials	Safety measures
<i>Strengthening the hip extensor muscles</i>	<i>While standing on one leg, with one hand supporting the body and the lower limb opposite the supporting leg extended. Perform a hip extension and return to the starting position</i>	<i>Increase hip extensor muscle strength</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>0.5-kg and 1.0-kg ankle weights.</i>	<i>Avoid using your core muscles and making improper compensations. Keep your torso upright.</i>
<i>Strengthening the hip abductor muscles</i>	<i>While standing on one leg with one hand supporting the body: extend the unsupported lower limb. Perform hip abduction to the full range of motion and return to the starting position.</i>	<i>Increase strength in hip abductor muscles; stimulate isometric contraction of the knee flexors</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>0.5-kg and 1.0-kg ankle weights</i>	<i>Avoid hip flexion and rotation, as well as knee extension. Pay attention to trunk alignment.</i>
<i>Strengthening of the hip abductor muscles and lower limb stability</i>	<i>While standing: a step will be placed next to the patient, who should step up and down completely using a sideways motion</i>	<i>Increase hip abductor strength; improve lower-body stability</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.</i>	<i>Step, 68x28x10 cm Chair</i>	<i>Avoid putting excessive strain on the knee joint when placing your foot on the step and on the floor. Maintain proper trunk alignment. Have a physical therapist present for support, if necessary</i>

Strength Training Exercises

Exercise elements	Exercise Description	Aim	Dosage minimum	Repetitions and intensity	Materials	Safety measures
Strengthening ankle flexors and extensors	While standing: rise onto your toes and lower yourself back down, supporting yourself with your hands on a chair. Stand on your heels and lower yourself back down, supporting yourself with your hands on the chair	Increase muscle strength in the ankle dorsiflexors and plantar flexors; improve ankle mobility.	2 sets of 10 repetitions, with both feet on the ground and hand support	2 sets of 10 repetitions, standing on one leg, without using your hands for support	Chair	Older adults with foot deformities will be able to maintain the recommended positions for a shorter period of time.
Functional training: sit-to-stand	Sit with your feet flat on the floor, move closer to the edge of the chair, lean your torso forward by bending your hips, and push your body upward by extending your torso and lower limbs	To practice the postural adjustments and muscle recruitment necessary for transferring from a sitting to a standing position; to improve functional independence	2 sets of 10 repetitions	2 séries de 10 repetições, sem apoio dos membros superiores.	Chair	Note strain on the knee joint
Strengthening the knee extensor muscles	While seated, perform knee extensions starting at 90 degrees and progressing to 0 degrees.	Increase muscle strength of knee extensors	2 sets of 10 repetitions, starting weight of 0.5 kg.	2 sets of 10 repetitions with a 0.5 kg increase in weight	Chair and ankle weights	Supervision by a physical therapist. Pay attention to trunk posture while sitting.

3.1.4 Anticipatory Adjustment Exercises

The main objectives of this type of exercise are to practice anticipating adjustments in various directions and changing planes while improving focus.

The first exercise (anticipatory adjustment I) involves tapping the entire foot on a step as quickly as possible without stepping up. Older adults will be instructed to perform the movement without support. The exercise will be advanced by increasing the number of sets and the speed of the taps on the step. In the second exercise (anticipatory adjustment II), while standing, the older adult should take a lateral step, then a step forward, then a step backwards. Initially, the exercise will be performed in 10 steps, given a verbal command, with predetermined lower-limb directions (e.g., “right leg back; right leg forward; right leg to the side”). Progression involves increasing the number of sets, randomising the directions and lower-limb stepping, and increasing exercise speed (e.g., command: “left leg forward; right leg to the left; right leg backwards; left leg backwards”).

Postural Adjustment Exercises

Exercise elements	Exercise Description	Aim	Dosage minimum	Repetitions and intensity	Materials	Safety measures
<i>Postural adjustments I</i>	<i>Touch the ground with your entire foot on a step (without stepping up), as fast as possible;</i>	<i>Practice anticipatory adjustments in various directions and changes in plane Work on attention</i>	<i>1 set of 10 steps</i>	<i>3 sets of 10 steps</i>	<i>Step Chair for support if necessary</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
<i>Postural adjustments II</i>	<i>Take a side step, then a step forward and a step backward.</i>	<i>Practice anticipatory adjustments in various directions and changes in plane Work on attention</i>	<i>1 set of 10 steps in response to a verbal command (lower limb and predetermined directions)</i>	<i>3 sets of 10 steps, alternating the directions and the leg used for each step, and increasing the speed of the exercise.</i>	<i>Chair for support if necessary</i>	<i>Supervision</i>

3.1.5 Balance while standing still

At the end of the anticipatory adjustment training session, static balance exercises will be performed, comprising two types: 1 – while standing, the older adult will shift their weight laterally, forward, and backwards, with feet parallel and a stable base of support; and 2 – a full cone exercise using an ankle strategy. The aim is to improve stability limits and control of the centre of gravity's displacement, while encouraging the use of the ankle strategy. Progression will be achieved by increasing the number of exercise repetitions, with eyes closed and without manual support

In static balance training II, the participant must remain standing with a reduced base of support (semi-tandem). Progression will occur by altering the base of support (stable → unstable), through cervical rotation, and by closing the eyes during the exercise

The static balance training will progress in difficulty by altering the base of support, with changes in sensory and proprioceptive stimuli (stable and unstable surfaces—using mats), combined with visual (eyes open and closed) and vestibular (change in head position) inputs

3.1.6 Dynamic Balance (Moving)

Dynamic balance training will consist of circuits that include activities such as walking on a stable surface, reaching, walking on an unstable surface, and walking while navigating obstacles. Five tasks have been developed for each of these activities, identified by a number.

The circuit will be composed using one task from each activity. Example: all tasks numbered 1 from each activity make up the first circuit. As the program progresses, the circuit will consist of tasks numbered 2 from each activity. And so on.

Tasks 1, 2, and 3 will be performed by the group for two weeks each, and tasks 4 and 5 for three weeks each, totaling twelve weeks of training.

In each session, the older adults will complete the circuit three times. The first and second runs of the circuit will be unguided. During the third round, the therapist should intervene to encourage the older adult to perform the circuit stations optimally and assist with any necessary adjustments. Starting with the second round, participants should balance a plastic cup on their hand or hold a cup of water to practice dual-tasking.

Balance while standing

Exercise elements	Exercise Description	Aim	Dosage minimum	Repetitions and intensity	Materials	Safety measures
<i>Balance I</i>	<p>1- While standing: shift your weight side to side, forward, and backward, keeping your feet parallel and maintaining a comfortable stance.</p> <p>2- Full limits of stability cone exercise using ankle rotation.</p>	<p>Train stability limits and controlling the shift of the center of gravity. Encourage the use of the ankle strategy</p>	<p>1- 1 set of 5 repetitions in the same plane, on each side with hand support</p> <p>2- 3 repetitions, with hand support.</p>	<p>Follow a random verbal command with eyes closed, without hand support</p>	<p>Chair</p>	<p>Stay close to a chair or wall. Use it for support if you lose your balance. Supervise those who are less steady</p>
<i>Balance II</i>	<p>In an upright position with a reduced support base in the semi-tandem</p>	<p>Improve balance while standing</p>	<p>3 sets* of 10 seconds, feet in a semi-tandem stance, eyes open, and on a stable surface; *Focus on bilateral cervical rotation during the 2nd and 3rd sets of the exercise</p>	<p>3 sets* of 10 seconds, in the semi-tandem position, eyes closed, on 2 mats. *Guide bilateral cervical rotation during the 2nd and 3rd sets of the exercise.</p>	<p>Chair, 2 mats</p>	<p>Provide consistent support and monitor individuals who exhibit instability</p>

Balance while moving

Walking on a stable surface (line length: 3 meters)	1. Walk sideways along a line (first facing forward, then facing backward, and alternate between the two to work both sides equally)
	2. Tanden walking
	3. Tanden walking with head movements
	4. Tanden walking passing the ball back and forth with another person
	5. Tanden walking with eyes closed
Reach	1. Catch an object at medium height and throw it back above, or vice versa
	2. Catch an object at medium height and throw it back below, or vice versa
	3. Pick up an object from a low position and return it to a higher position, or vice versa
	4. Catch a sequence of objects: catch low and throw at medium height, catch at medium height and throw low
	5. Catching a sequence of objects: catch in the middle and throw back high, catch high and throw back low, catch low and throw back at medium height
Walking on a foam	1. Walking on a foam (1 mat)
	2. Side walking on a foam
	3. Side walking on a foam passing the ball back and forth with another person
	4. Walking on a foam (2 mats)
	5. Side walking on a foam (2 mats) passing the ball back and forth with another person
Walking with obstacles	1. Walking while stepping over obstacles at fixed intervals
	2. Walking while stepping over obstacles at varying intervals
	3. Walk across the first step, step up onto the second step, and step across the third step
	4. Walk across the first step, step up onto the second step, step across the third step, and step up onto the fourth step
	5. Walk across the first step, step up onto the second step, walk across the third step, and step up onto the fourth step
Walking while turning around obstacles	1. Go around two obstacles (spaced 50 cm apart) by performing a full figure-eight movement.
	1. Go around three obstacles (spaced 50 cm apart) by performing a full figure-eight movement.
	1. Go around four obstacles (spaced 50 cm apart) by performing a full figure-eight movement.
	1. Go around five obstacles (spaced 50 cm apart) by performing a full figure-eight movement.
	1. Go around six obstacles (spaced 50 cm apart) by performing a full figure-eight movement.
Note: The first and second rounds of the circuit will be performed freely. During the third round, the therapist should intervene and	

	encourage the older adult to perform the circuit stations correctly, assisting with any necessary adjustments. (Starting with the second round, participants should balance a plastic cup in their hand or hold a plastic cup filled with water)
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Equilíbrio Dinâmico
(circuito)

A Marcha com diminuição de base

B Alcance

C Marcha em oito

D Marcha sobre superfície instável

E Marcha com obstáculos

Progression of in loco Exercises

Strengthening of ankle flexors and extensors

Baseline	Bipodal base, with hand support, 2 sets of 10 reps
1 st progression	Bipodal base, without hand support, 2 set of 10 reps
2 nd progression	Unipedal base, with hand support, 2 sets of 10 reps in each leg
3 rd progression	Unipedal base, without hand support, 2 set of 10 reps in each leg

Sit-to-stand

Baseline	Participant sits with both feet flat on the floor and uses their hands for support as they perform the movement to stand up from the chair, 2 sets of 10 reps
progression	Without hands support, 2 sets of 10 reps

Strengthening of knee extensors, hip extensors, abductors

Baseline	0.5 kg weight, 2 sets of 10 reps
Progressions	Sessions 1 and 2: no weight Sessions 3 and 4: 0.5 kg Sessions 5, 6, and 7: 1.0 kg Sessions 8, 9, and 10: 1.5 kg Sessions 11 and 12: 2.0 kg

Hip abduction and stability

Baseline	Participant should stand upright with a 0.5 kg weight on the distal end of the lower limb, step up onto a step using a lateral step, and perform two sets of 10 repetitions for each limb.
Progressions	Sessions 1 and 2: no weight Sessions 3 and 4: 0.5 kg Sessions 5, 6, and 7: 1.0 kg Sessions 8, 9, and 10: 1.5 kg Sessions 11 and 12: 2.0 kg

Postural adjustments I

Baseline	Tap the entire foot on a step (without stepping up), alternating as quickly as possible. 1 set of 10 taps.
1 st progression	2 sets of 10 taps
2 nd progression	3 sets of 10 taps

Postural adjustments II

Baseline	Upon verbal command, take a side step, a step forward, and a step backward with one leg, then the other. 1 set of 10 steps in all directions.
1 st progression	2 sets of 10 random steps (legs/directions)
2 nd progression	3 sets of 10 random steps (legs/directions)

Balance while standing I

Baseline	The patient, in a standing position, will perform lateral, anterior, and posterior weight-shifting exercises—1 set of 5 repetitions on each side, followed by a full cone walk using the ankle strategy—1 set of 3 repetitions with manual support, eyes open.
1 st progression	Follow random instructions
2 nd progression	Perform lateral, anterior, and posterior weight shifts—1 set of 5 repetitions on each side, finishing with a full cone exercise using ankle control—1 set of 3 repetitions without hand support, with eyes closed
3 rd progression	Follow Random instructions, without hand support, with eyes closed

Balance while standing II

Baseline	Stable surface, eyes open, feet in a semi-tandem stance, 3 sets of 10 seconds
1 st progression	Stable surface, eyes closed, feet in a semi-tandem stance, 3 sets of 10 seconds
2 nd progression	Standing on a foam (2 mats), eyes open, feet in a semi-tandem stance, 3 sets of 10 seconds
3 rd progression	Standing on a foam (2 mats), eyes closed, feet in a semi-tandem stance, 3 sets of 10 seconds

3.2 Exercícios domiciliares

3.2.1 General orientation

Participants will be instructed to follow the home exercise protocol according to the following safety criteria: 1. supervision by a family member or caregiver; 2. a suitable location with good lighting and ventilation; 3. proper use of support, such as near a table or chair or in a corner of the room.

At the initial assessment, each participant will receive a detailed instruction manual with written and illustrated exercises, including the recommended sequence and guidance on rest intervals between sets. In the intervention group, guidance on home exercises will be provided during the on-site exercise sessions (12 sessions). During the first four on-site sessions, home exercises will be performed, and guidance will be provided at the end of each session, so the on-site exercise sequence will be adjusted to prevent repetition. From the fifth to the ninth session, following the on-site exercise protocol, a brief review of the home exercises will be conducted (10–15 minutes). In the final three exercise sessions, the home exercises will again be performed and guided at the end of the therapy, requiring adjustments to the on-site exercise sequence to avoid repetition.

During the exercise program (12 weeks) and throughout the study follow-up, older adults will be encouraged to record in their fall diaries whether they have performed the home exercises. This information will be verified monthly by the research assistant, who will contact participants in both the control and intervention groups by phone. Therefore, the diaries will not be collected weekly and will be collected 6 months and 1 year after the initial assessment.

3.2.2 Home-based Exercises Program

The home exercise protocol includes six exercises, such as static balance and muscle-strengthening activities. These home exercises are the same as the in-clinic ones (plantar flexors and hip abductors—standing), and the squat exercise will be advanced, while the other exercises (static balance training and upper limb strengthening) will remain in a single form without progression. The progression of the home exercises will occur alongside the progression of the on-site exercises. At the end of this period, the patient will perform the most advanced level achieved at home. Guidance on progression will be tailored to the individual.

Home exercises should be preceded by a warm-up, performed while sitting in a chair with a backrest, and consist of freely moving the feet for one minute.

Of the six exercises performed at home, three are carried out in the same way as those done at the clinic (plantar flexors, sit-to-stand, and hip abductors—standing).

The starting position for the fourth exercise is standing with both feet on the ground, with the heel of one foot aligned with the inner edge of the opposite foot (semi-tandem stance). The exercise involves slowly turning the head to the right and left (3 sets of 10 seconds each). The fifth exercise will be dynamic balance training while walking in a straight line for approximately 3 metres. The professional responsible for the intervention should encourage participants to perform the exercises in a safe location under supervision.

The sixth and final exercise will be performed in a standing position with both feet on the ground. The number of sets and repetitions should be applied to each upper limb. Each limb will move from the starting position of adduction, extension, and internal shoulder rotation, crossing the body's midline (the hand performing the exercise positioned over the contralateral anterior superior iliac spine) to the final position of abduction, flexion, and external shoulder rotation, keeping the elbow extended and tracing a simple diagonal path. The individual should follow the movement with their gaze.

The optimal exercise regimen for each participant will be regularly assessed and adjusted by the responsible physical therapists to ensure that the programme remains challenging as the older adults' performance improves.

Progression of home-based exercises

Home exercises should be prescribed from the first exercise session. The exercises' descriptions and instructions are detailed in the Fall Prevention Program's guidance manual. Older adults will receive the necessary materials to perform exercises at home, such as ankle weights with loads of 0.5 kg, 1.0 kg, and 2.0 kg. The progression of home exercises should align with the level of exercises performed at the facility.

The home exercises are described below. 1) Warm-up: active ankle exercises (dorsiflexion/plantarflexion, eversion/inversion, circumduction);

2) Strengthening of the plantar flexors;

3) Strengthening of knee extensors;

4) Strengthening of hip abductors;

5) Static balance II (semi-tandem);

6) Dynamic balance (tandem walking);

7) Upper limb diagonal

Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6	Week 7	Week 8	Week 9	Week 10	Week 11	Week 12
<i>in loco</i> exercises without weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises without weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 0.5 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 0.5 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1.5 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1.5 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 1.5 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 2 kg weight	<i>in loco</i> exercises 2 kg weight
Guidance and execution of home exercises	Guidance and execution of home exercises	Guidance and execution of home exercises	Guidance and execution of home exercises	Brief review of home exercises (10–15 min)	Execution of home exercises	Execution of home exercises	Execution of home exercises				

Adverse Event Report Form Related to Exercise

Date: _____

Name: _____ Nº. register: _____

Week of e intervention:

(2) (3) (4) (5) (6) (7) (8) (9) (10) (11) (12)

1. Have you experienced any of the problems listed below this week that you believe are related to the exercise you have been doing?

(1) pain (2) exhaustion (3) edema (4) others _____

2. If you felt pain, please indicate where it was:

3. On a scale of 0 (no pain) to 10 (maximum pain), how would you rate the pain you experienced this week? _____

4. Did this problem (pain, fatigue, swelling, etc.) prevent you from carrying out your usual activities?

(1) No (2) Yes, a little (3) Yes, a lot (4) Yes, extremely

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Centre

ID of Participant: _____

ADVERSE EVENT REPORT FORM

Did the participant experience any adverse effects from the exercise during the study? [] YES [] NO
(If yes, please fill in the details below)

Severity	Was it related to the study?	Action Taken in Response to the Study's Findings	Adverse Event (AE) Outcome	Was it expected?	Severe
1 = mild 2 = moderate 3 = severe	1 = Definitely related 2 = Possibly related 3 = Not related	1 = None 2 = Permanently discontinued 3 = Temporarily discontinued 4 = Reduced dosage (repetitions and/or load) 5 = Started medication to relieve symptoms	1 = Resolved, no injuries 2 = EA still present, not treated 3 = EA still present, but being treated 4 = Residual effects, untreated 5 = Residual effects, being treated 6 = Death 7 = Unknown	1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No

Adverse Event	Start Date	End Date	Severity	Study related	What was done?	Outcome	Was it expected	Severe	Initials the of assessor
1.									
2.									
3.									